

Achievement Goal Orientation Prompts in Interleaving-Based Worked Examples: Effects on Transfer, Cognitive Load, And Motivation

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 10 October 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Nurul Amini</p>	<p>This study aims to analyze the effects of achievement goal orientation (AGO) prompts in interleaving-based worked example learning on students' transfer ability, cognitive load, and learning motivation. The research employed two fully randomized experiments. The first experiment compared worked example learning with problem-solving, while the second applied a 2×2 factorial design to examine the interaction between learning design (interleaving vs. blocked) and AGO prompt type (mastery vs. performance). The findings revealed that worked examples significantly enhanced transfer ability while reducing cognitive load. Furthermore, interleaving proved more effective than blocked practice, particularly in promoting both near and far transfer and mitigating working memory depletion. AGO prompts also positively influenced students' motivation, especially in fostering mastery orientation. These results highlight that interleaving-based worked examples can serve as an effective instructional strategy for strengthening transfer and cognitive efficiency, while AGO prompts play a crucial role in improving students' motivation, particularly for those with a mastery approach.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: achievement goal orientation, cognitive load, interleaving, transfer, worked example</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Mathematics learning in schools is still largely dominated by blocked practice (e.g., AAABBB). Although this approach gives the impression of ease, a number of studies show that blocked practice can cause boredom, lead to working memory (WM) depletion, and hinder deeper conceptual understanding (Jackson et al., 2014; Smallwood & Schooler, 2006). As an alternative, the interleaving strategy (e.g., ABABAB) presents concepts alternately, thereby encouraging the process of comparing questions, forming a more flexible knowledge scheme, and proving to be more effective in improving conceptual understanding and transfer ability. However, this strategy is also often considered more challenging for students (Hartwig et al., 2022; Do & Thomas, 2023).

The effectiveness of interleaving can be explained through the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) framework, which emphasises the importance of managing cognitive load. The demand to distinguish similar concepts within the same domain has the potential to increase intrinsic cognitive load. To overcome this condition, this study uses a worked example approach to reduce initial processing load and shift

some of that load to germane load which supports scheme formation (Sweller et al., 2019).

In addition to cognitive factors, the success of learning strategies that demand high cognitive load is also influenced by motivational aspects. Adequate motivation enables students to allocate cognitive resources optimally, thereby strengthening the learning process (Likourezos & Kalyuga, 2017). In this context, Achievement Goal Orientation (AGO) is a relevant theoretical framework for understanding students' learning goal orientation. The mastery approach orientation focuses on deep understanding, while the performance approach orientation emphasises achieving excellence relative to others (Elliot & McGregor, 2001).

Various studies show that AGO not only affects learning motivation but also has implications for students' use of cognitive strategies and transfer abilities (Howell & Watson, 2007; Mouratidis et al., 2018). However, studies that integrate interleaving, worked examples, and AGO simultaneously in the context of mathematics learning at the secondary school level are still very limited. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by examining the effects of

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learning design and achievement goal orientation prompts based on worked examples on students' transfer abilities, cognitive load, and goal orientation.

Cognitive Load Theory (CLT) emphasises how humans process information during learning, paying attention to the limitations of working memory capacity and the role of long-term memory (Sweller, 1988; Kalyuga, 2011a). Effective instructional design should minimise unnecessary cognitive load so that working memory capacity can be used to build schemes in long-term memory and support knowledge transfer (Chen et al., 2019; Sweller, van Merriënboer, et al., 1998).

According to CLT, there are three types of cognitive load among others:

1. Intrinsic Cognitive Load

Load is determined by the complexity of the material and the interactions between elements that must be processed simultaneously. The level must be adjusted to the students' abilities to prevent overload and ensure that the schemes built are effective (Sweller, van Merriënboer, et al., 1998; Kalyuga, 2011; Schnotz & Kürschner, 2007).

2. Extraneous Cognitive Load

Load resulting from suboptimal presentation of material, such as split attention or redundancy. This load is unnecessary and can be minimised through clear and systematic instructional design, allowing students to focus on relevant information (Sweller, Ayres, & Kalyuga, 2011; Van Merriënboer et al., 2002; Likourezos et al., 2019).

3. Germane Cognitive Load

Productive load that supports scheme construction in long-term memory. Increased germane load promotes deep understanding, knowledge automation, and transferability. Strategies such as introducing problem variation can stimulate the development of more optimal cognitive schemes (van Merriënboer & Ayres, 2005; Kalyuga, 2011b). Effective management of cognitive load, by reducing extraneous load, adjusting intrinsic load, and increasing germane load, is a key factor in designing efficient learning that supports student knowledge transfer.

Worked example is a fully solved problem that students can study as a guide for problem-solving (Atkinson et al., 2000). Within the framework of Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), this strategy reduces extraneous load, manages intrinsic load, and enhances germane load, thereby making learning more efficient (Paas & van Merriënboer, 2020).

The effect of worked examples can be explained through the borrowing and reorganizing principle, in which learners borrow knowledge from external sources and reorganize it within their cognitive structures (Chen et al., 2023). This approach is more effective than unguided problem solving,

which carries the risk of overloading working memory. Worked examples are particularly beneficial for novice learners and for materials with high element interactivity, as explicit guidance can lower cognitive load and prevent split-attention and redundancy effects (Sweller et al., 2011). Accordingly, worked example-based instructional design is recommended to improve both learning efficiency and quality.

The following illustrates the worked example design employed in the present study.

==WORKED EXAMPLE ==

MENENTUKAN PENYELESAIAN PERSAMAAN DAN PERTIDAKSAMAN LINEAR SATU VARIABEL

Contoh [1]
Berat badan ayah adalah 5 kali berat badan Bobi dikurangi 10 kg. Jika berat ayah adalah 80 kg, berapakah berat badan Bobi?

Penyelesaian:

Langkah 1. (buat pemisalan setiap variabel)
 Misal: Berat badan Ayah = a
 Berat badan Bobi = b

Langkah 2. (buat model matematika dari kalimat soal)
 $a = 5b - 10$
 $a = 80$ } $5b - 10 = 80$

Langkah 3. (Substitusi dan penyelesaian linear satu variabel)
 $5b - 10 = 80$
 $5b - 10 + (10) = 80 + (10)$ [kedua ruas ditambah dengan (10) karena $-10 + (10) = 0$]
 $5b = 90$
 $5b \times (\frac{1}{5}) = 90 \times (\frac{1}{5})$ [kedua ruas dikali dengan ($\frac{1}{5}$) karena $5 \times (\frac{1}{5}) = 1$]
 $b = 18$

Langkah 4. (Menjawab pertanyaan dan kesimpulan)
 Jadi, berat badan Bobi adalah 18 kg

Figure 1. Worked Example Design

Interleaving is a learning strategy that presents exercises from various topics alternately, in contrast to blocked practice, which presents topics separately (Carvalho & Goldstone, 2019; Hartwig et al., 2022). Research shows that interleaving is superior to blocked practice in improving long-term retention, conceptual understanding, and transfer ability (Foster et al., 2019; Rohrer et al., 2020).

From the perspective of CLT, interleaving does increase intrinsic cognitive load because students must repeatedly distinguish between different types of tasks (Chen, Retnowati, Castro-Alonso, et al., 2023). However, the variety of problems presented creates desirable difficulty that strengthens discrimination skills, prevents boredom, and optimises germane cognitive load for cognitive scheme formation (Bjork & Bjork, 2011; Sweller, Ayres, & Kalyuga, 2011). Such cognitive challenges not only require cognitive capacity but also motivational support to keep students engaged in the learning process. Thus, the effectiveness of interleaving is greatly influenced by the goal orientation of the students.

Achievement Goal Orientation (AGO) is a conceptual framework for understanding the goals underlying student learning behaviour (Elliot & McGregor, 2001). In general, AGO consists of two main dimensions, namely mastery goals and performance goals, each of which is divided into approach and avoidance orientations. Mastery approach reflects efforts to develop competence and deep understanding, while mastery avoidance emphasises avoiding mistakes or loss of ability. Conversely, performance approach focuses on demonstrating superiority over others,

while performance avoidance is oriented towards avoiding poor performance.

Previous research shows that mastery orientation, particularly mastery approach, is positively associated with learning strategies that support concept elaboration, self-regulation, and deep understanding (Hulleman et al., 2010; Senko & Dawson, 2017). Meanwhile, performance approach orientation can increase effort in competitive contexts, although it often shifts students' attention from the process to the final outcome (Harackiewicz et al., 2002). Thus, mastery orientation is more aligned with challenge-based learning (desirable difficulty), while performance orientation tends to be effective when success is associated with social recognition.

II. METHOD

The research employed a fully randomized experimental design, in which all students were randomly selected and then regrouped into new classes to ensure balanced distribution. The study consisted of two experiments conducted sequentially.

1. Experiment 1

a. Method

In Experiment 1, the design employed was a Posttest-Only Control Group Design, with two classes randomly selected and then assigned as the experimental group and the control group.

b. Participants

This study involved 60 seventh-grade students randomly selected from the junior high school student population. Participants were divided into two groups, namely the worked example group ($n = 30$) and the problem-solving group ($n = 30$). The average age of students in the worked example group was 13.64 years ($S.D. = 8.66$), while in the problem-solving group it was 13.46 years ($S.D. = 9.16$). All students were novices to the material on single variable linear equations and inequalities being taught.

c. Material

The learning materials in this study were structured into three phases: Introductory, Acquisition, and Test. In the Introductory phase, students reviewed fundamental concepts of algebra, algebraic operations, and sets, followed by an understanding of linear equations and inequalities in one variable. The Acquisition phase emphasized skills in translating problems into mathematical form and solving linear equations and inequalities in one variable. Finally, in the Test phase, students were presented with real-world contextual problems to assess their ability to apply the acquired knowledge.

d. Procedures

Before the experiment began, the school teachers introduced the researchers to the students. Then, an introductory phase was conducted to review the prerequisite material and basic material on Single variable linear equations (SVLE) and single variable linear inequalities (SVLI). In this phase, both classes received the same treatment, including the duration of learning time. After that, in the acquisition phase, the experimental group received instruction using worked examples (WE), while the control group received problem solving based instruction. Each student was given 3 minutes to study and work on each question at this stage. After the learning phase, students took a near transfer test for 14 minutes and a far transfer test for 18 minutes and filled out a cognitive load measurement instrument.

2. Experiment 2

a. Method

Experiment 2 employed a 2×2 between-subjects factorial design, with two main variables: instructional design (interleaving vs. blocked) and achievement goal orientation (mastery approach vs. performance approach).

b. Participants

A total of 122 seventh-grade junior high school students were randomly assigned to four experimental groups. The Interleaving–Mastery Approach group (ID-MA) comprised 18 male and 14 female students ($M = 13.50$ years, $SD = 0.41$). The Interleaving–Performance Approach group (ID-PA) included 12 male and 18 female students ($M = 13.34$ years, $SD = 0.41$). The Blocked–Mastery Approach group (BD-MA) consisted of 12 male and 18 female students ($M = 13.41$ years, $SD = 0.36$). The Blocked–Performance Approach group (BD-PA) comprised 11 male and 19 female students ($M = 13.35$ years, $SD = 0.33$). Due to the randomization process, one group contained 32 students, whereas the remaining three groups consisted of 30 students each. All participants were novices, with prior learning experiences limited to conventional classroom instruction.

c. Material

The materials in Experiment 2 were also structured into three phases. The Introductory phase was identical to that in Experiment 1, focusing on a review of prerequisite knowledge. The Acquisition phase was based on the outcomes of Experiment 1 and consisted of worked examples (WE) on the topics of Linear Equations in One Variable (LEOV) and Linear Inequalities in One Variable (LIOV). The WEs were developed in four instructional designs: (1) interleaving–mastery, in which LEOV and LIOV problems were presented alternately with prompts

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emphasizing deep understanding; (2) interleaving–performance, in which problems were presented alternately with prompts emphasizing outperforming peers; (3) blocked–mastery, in which problems were presented by topic separately and sequentially with prompts emphasizing deep understanding; and (4) blocked–performance, in which problems were presented by topic separately and sequentially with prompts emphasizing outperforming peers. The Test phase was similar to that in Experiment 1 but was supplemented with additional instruments, namely the achievement goal orientation (AGO) questionnaire and a working memory depletion measure.

d. Procedures

The procedure for experiment 2 was similar to that of experiment 1, including the duration of the experiment. The main differences were the provision of achievement goal orientation (AGO) prompts before studying the worked examples (WE), the addition of a depletion test after the treatment to measure working memory depletion, and the completion of a questionnaire as a manipulation check for the prompts given.

III. RESULT

1. Experiment 1

The results of the analysis showed a significant difference in near transfer ability between the WE and PS groups, $t(58) = 3.947$, $p < 0.001$, with the experimental group scoring higher. Far transfer ability also showed a significant difference, $t(58) = 2.670$, $p = 0.010$. For cognitive load, the analysis showed significant differences in near transfer, $t(58) = -2.012$, $p = 0.049$, and in far transfer, $t(58) = -2.918$, $p = 0.005$, with the WE group experiencing lower cognitive load than the PS group. These findings indicate that the WE treatment not only improved near and far transfer abilities but also reduced students' cognitive load on both types of tasks. The significant results across all variables provide a strong basis for proceeding to experiment 2, which aims to test the generalisation of the findings in a different learning context.

2. Experiment 2

a. Main effect of Learning Design

ANOVA analysis showed that the learning design had a significant effect on near transfer, $F(1,120) = 15.596$, $p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.117$. A significant effect was also found on far transfer, $F(1,120) = 10.168$, $p = 0.002$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.079$. In addition, the learning design had a significant effect on working memory, $F(1,120) = 11.101$, $p = 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.086$. The mean and standard deviation values of each group's scores are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for the Main Effect of Learning Design in Experiment 2

Measurement Data	Learning Design	
	Interleaving (n=62) M(SD)	Blocked (n=60) M(SD)
Near Transfer	2,69 (0,951)	1,92 (1,293)
Far Transfer	2.08 (1.045)	1.47 (1.081)
WM Depletion	20.395 (20.38)	20.700 (22.70)

b. Main effect of Achievement Goal Orientation (AGO) Prompt

The provision of AGO prompts showed a significant effect on motivation levels in near transfer, $F(1,120) = 10.997$, $p = 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.085$, as well as on motivation levels in far transfer, $F(1,120) = 18.578$, $p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.136$. The mean and standard deviation values of each group's scores are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for the Main Effect of AGO Prompt in Experiment 2

Measurement Data	Achievement Goal Orientation Prompt	
	Mastery Approach (n=62) M (S.D.)	Performance Approach (n=60) M (S.D.)
Motivation towards Near Transfer	5.90 (1.168)	5.10 (1.458)
Motivation towards Far Transfer	5.92 (1.167)	4.881.487)

c. Interaction Effects

Furthermore, there was a significant interaction between the learning design and AGO prompt on near transfer, $F(1,120) = 4.878$, $p = 0.029$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.040$. Post hoc tests revealed that students who learned with interleaving accompanied by a mastery prompt obtained significantly higher near transfer scores than those who learned with interleaving accompanied by a performance prompt ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, in the blocked design, no significant difference was found between the mastery prompt and the performance prompt.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of experiment 1 show that the use of worked examples (WE) significantly improves students near transfer and far transfer abilities compared to conventional problem solving (PS). This finding is consistent with cognitive load

theory (CLT), which states that presenting structured solution steps can reduce extraneous cognitive load, allowing working memory capacity to be allocated to more productive information processing and scheme construction in long-term memory (Sweller, 1988; Sweller, Ayres, & Kalyuga, 2011). These results are also in line with previous studies showing that worked examples are effective in facilitating the understanding of complex material in novice students (Paas & Van Merriënboer, 1994; Chen et al., 2019).

In addition to improving transfer ability, worked examples have been shown to reduce students' cognitive load in both near and far transfer tasks. This reduction in cognitive load indicates that structured instructional design can minimise irrelevant cognitive activity (extraneous load), allowing students to focus on knowledge construction efforts (germane load) (Kalyuga, 2011; Van Merriënboer & Sweller, 2005). In other words, worked examples not only facilitate understanding but also optimise working memory capacity for deeper learning.

The results of experiment 2 show that the interleaving strategy is significantly more effective than blocked practice in improving both near transfer and far transfer abilities. This advantage can be explained through the cognitive mechanisms activated by interleaving, particularly problem discrimination and the formation of flexible conceptual schemes. In near transfer, interleaving encourages discriminative contrast by requiring students to compare and contrast various types of questions presented alternately. This process improves students' ability to distinguish conceptual characteristics and apply knowledge more flexibly to similar new situations (Kornell & Bjork, 2008; Do & Thomas, 2023).

In contrast, blocked practice, which only presents homogeneous questions repeatedly, makes students rely more on routine procedures without deep conceptual understanding (Chen et al., 2021). In addition, interleaving creates desirable difficulties (David, 2023), although slowing down initial mastery, actually strengthens long-term retention and conceptual understanding. The results of this study also reveal that interleaving combined with a performance approach produces a stronger effect, as students with this orientation are more motivated to face the challenge of complex problem variations (Senko & Harackiewicz, 2005; Chazan et al., 2022).

In far transfer, the effectiveness of interleaving can be explained through the Cognitive Load Theory framework, particularly the concept of element interactivity. The variety of questions in interleaving encourages students to differentiate and connect concepts, thereby increasing germane cognitive load that supports flexibility in thinking and the formation of more robust conceptual schemes (Hartwig et al., 2022; Chen, Retnowati, Castro-Alonso, et al., 2023). Conversely, blocked practice, which focuses only

on repeating similar questions, fails to provide cognitive challenges, resulting in shallow learning limited to the initial practice context.

The interleaving strategy did not show a significant difference in cognitive load. Although interleaving increases intrinsic load through the process of comparing and distinguishing questions, this load is functional because it contributes to germane load that supports scheme formation (Sweller et al., 2019). Conversely, blocked practice is more likely to produce extraneous load due to low variation, but this effect is balanced by additional instructions before the test. Thus, although not statistically significant, interleaving still produces a quality of cognitive load that is more conducive to learning than blocked practice.

The results of this study also indicate that achievement goal orientation (AGO) prompts consistently increase mastery-based motivation, but not significantly on performance orientation. Intrinsic mastery motivation encourages a focus on understanding and self-development (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Conversely, performance motivation requires external support in the form of rewards or social evaluation (Boissicat et al., 2021). These findings confirm that mastery-based strategies are more effective for maintaining long-term motivation.

Research on working memory (WE) depletion shows that in interleaved learning, students are required to differentiate, compare, and integrate concepts from various types of questions, thereby placing greater demands on working memory (working memory load). Despite increasing these demands, interleaving has the potential to minimise working memory depletion. This is because interleaving presents a variety of questions that prevent monotony and boredom, as occurs in blocked practice (Sana & Yan, 2022).

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results, the interleaving strategy was proven to be effective in improving students' near and far transfer abilities and reducing working memory depletion. In addition, the achievement goal orientation (AGO) prompt was proven to be effective in increasing student motivation, particularly the mastery approach orientation. Furthermore, there was a significant interaction effect between the interleaving learning design and the AGO prompt on near transfer abilities, indicating that the combination of the two contributed more significantly to improving student learning outcomes.

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